

Project Dissemination and Communication Materials including website, press pack, posters, videos, brochures and banners

Deliverable 8.2

Prepared by ICLEI EUROPE

Date: 30/04/2018

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant
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	Document:	D8.2. Project Dissemination and Communication materials, including videos, website, press pack, posters, brochures and banners		
	Author:	ICLEI Europe	Version:	1
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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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Responsible Partner: ICLEI Europe

WP: WP 8

Task: Task 8.2

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Dissemination level	
X	PU = Public
	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

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Approvals

ICLEI Europe, CIRCE

	Company
Author/s	ICLEI Europe
Task Leader	ICLEI Europe
WP Leader	ICLEI Europe

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document comprises the series of dissemination and communications products produced during the first 12 months of the CIRC-PACK Horizon 2020 project (to end April 2018).

This document, 'Project Dissemination and Communication Materials', therefore provides an overview of the project's constituent dissemination and communications products, ranging from visual identity to the project website, from project leaflets and posters to the generic project PowerPoint presentation and so forth. These elements are essential components for a given project to run successfully and professionally, and a typical part of any Horizon 2020 initiative.

The visual identity of the CIRC-PACK project is an important first step in establishing not only the identity and very basis for the project, but also in branding the various products which are used to 'spread the word' about the project before and after project results are delivered. Visual identity includes the name, logo and of course the rules of graphic layout and use of the logo for those who will deploy it – in this case the project partners.

This document also provides a brief project description, and of course summarises the work which has been done on the all-important project website. As concerns other communications and dissemination materials such as leaflets, posters and roll-up banners, screenshots of these products will also be provided. Regarding the templates which have been created under the project's visual identity (templates for Word documents and PowerPoints), screenshots of these products are also included in this deliverable. In addition, a brief overview of social media communications is given. Finally, information regarding the project's forthcoming video materials is included, to provide an idea of the importance of disseminating information in video form to both public and other stakeholders.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an easy accessible overview, but of course more in-depth information on the various dissemination and communications materials is available upon request if the need arises.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 8.2 of the CIRC-PACK Horizon 2020 project comprises the series of dissemination and communications products produced during the first 12 months of the project (to end April 2018); part of CIRC-PACK Work Package 8, ‘Awareness, dissemination, communication’.

The relevant materials are included in this document in summarised form for ease of review, but one or any product is available upon request in original .pdf format for the purposes of more extensive review.

Deliverable 8.2, which is the outcome of Task 8.2 in the CIRC-PACK Document of Work, has been led by ICLEI Europe (denoted as ‘ICLEI EURO’ in the project Document of Work). Deliverable 8.2 is a direct result of the objectives established in Task 8.1 and Deliverable 8.1., the ‘Dissemination and Communication Plan’; during which target audiences, key messages and main communications channels were identified for the remainder of the CIRC-PACK project.

Project description

CIRC-PACK (Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain) is a three-year, EU-funded project that aims to develop a more sustainable plastics sector. This means less dependence on fossil fuels and a more efficient, competitive and integrated value chain for the circular economy of the future.

Specifically, and through its three ‘demo cases’, the project consortium is working to: (i) decouple the plastics value chain from fossil feedstock by producing new bio-based polyesters; (ii) introduce eco-friendly, innovative packaging designs, and; (iii) enhance sorting and recycling processes to create an affective “after-use” plastics economy.

The CIRC-PACK project is composed of a multi-disciplinary consortium of 22 partners from seven European countries, integrating non-profit organizations, municipalities, research organizations, large companies and SMEs.

Visual identity

Prior to the production of the required dissemination and communications materials for the project, the first priority has been to establish a visual identity; namely a logo and graphic design (rules) appropriate to the name and branding of the CIRC-PACK project.

Evidently, the name of the project itself reflects the circular economy-oriented objectives of the project and its clear relation to the production/design of new packaging materials and the manner in which they are sorted and recycled. In this way, for the project partners “CIRC-PACK” has already become synonymous with innovation and ‘closing the loop’ in the plastic packaging economy.

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The logo of the CIRC-PACK project (below) is now a branding necessity in all products and materials, and is required to provide consistent visual identity which reflects the aforementioned concepts that are central to the project itself.

Following discussion with the contracted graphic design agency, ICLEI Europe was able to propose this logo in multiple formats, such as .jpeg, .png and 'vector', as well as in black and white and monochromatic as opposed to colour. This is owing to the need for logo use across a variety of media and products, i.e. website and social media such as Twitter, but also printed materials such as leaflets/brochures and roll-up banners with different graphical and visual requirements.

Finally, a seven-page graphic manual for CIRC-PACK logos and visuals was prepared (i.e. below), with clear rules and guidelines for both CIRC-PACK logos and European Union-related graphics.

Written identity

An additional, crucial component of CIRC-PACK's identity is the written identity of the project – designed to provide consistent messaging regardless of the type of publication and length of text.

Specifically, this means that messaging will be consistent whether the author uses a tagline, single sentence, a set of bullet points, half a page, or indeed provides an overview of technologies. For all these formats, a set text has been created and is available to all partners in the 'Written Identity' document.

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2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PRODUCTS

This section of the document comprises an overview of the primary dissemination and communication materials which have been prepared by ICLEI Europe (in conjunction with the relevant design agency) during the first 12 months of the project. These products constitute the bulk of CIRC-PACK Deliverable 8.2, and are represented here in screen shot exemplars.

2.1 Project Website

The CIRC-PACK project website can be viewed via www.circpack.eu. The platform is designed to provide a contemporary window and introduction to the project, as well as increasing volumes of information and content as it becomes populated with news, events and of course project results. The website is consistent with the visual identity and brand of the CIRC-PACK project, and can be easily managed by ICLEI Europe via the Typo3 platform/ content management system. The website also serves as a launch site for the forthcoming project newsletters and social media platforms (Twitter and LinkedIn).

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CP
ABOUT SOLUTIONS NEWS EVENTS MEDIA

CIRC-PACK CONSORTIUM

The CIRC-PACK consortium includes 22 partners across the plastic packaging waste value chain, including plastic suppliers, converters, retailers, waste recovery managers from the public and the private sector, research organisations and non-profits. They come from six European countries: Croatia, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, The Netherlands, plus Turkey.

This diverse group of partners has joined forces to reinvent and develop more sustainable, re-usable forms of plastic packaging and support market uptake of the developed solutions. The aim is to promote a transition to a circular economy contributing to the achievement of EU waste management and recycling targets by 2030.

CIRC-PACK partners along the value chain

CIRCE fosters energy efficiency improvements and the use of renewable energy. CIRCE's R&D&I and training activities respond to the needs of producers.

AITIP prepares the plastic industry for the utilisation of biobased materials, the improvement of eco-design and an effective post recycling economy.

ABOUT SOLUTIONS NEWS EVENTS MEDIA
In

MEDIA

Project factsheet

Looking for pre-written texts on the project's objectives, approach and key messages? We have prepared a document that includes project descriptions of various lengths, bullet points, and key messages from the project.

Download project factsheet

CIRC-PACK Logo

The CIRC-PACK logo is available in various formats. When using the CIRC-PACK logo, you must respect the guidelines set out in the [Graphic Manual](#), including acknowledging the support received under the EU's Horizon 2020 programme in project materials.

Download CIRC-PACK logo package

PARTNERS

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2.2 Dissemination: Leaflets, posters and roll-up banner

In order to support the project partners/ consortium throughout the duration of the CIRC-PACK project, a series of printed products are required for the project's many events (seminars, workshops, conference presence, etc.). Specifically, this includes a large number of leaflets/brochures, a smaller number of posters, and two roll-up banners which can be taken to a given event.

Leaflet

The leaflet/brochure below provides an introduction to the project consortium, project objectives and of course web site and social media details for the reader. This leaflet has already been circulated widely at several events and will continue to be useful for the remainder of the project.

PROJECT PARTNERS

CONTACT

info@circpack.eu
@circ_economy #circpack
linkedin.com/groups/12055948

FROM WASTE TO RESOURCE

ABOUT THE PROJECT

PLASTIC PACKAGING AND THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY

THE CIRC-PACK APPROACH

DEMO CASE A: PLASTICS FROM RENEWABLE RESOURCES

DEMO CASE B: ECO-FRIENDLY PACKAGING DESIGNS

DEMO CASE C: ENHANCED SORTING AND RECYCLING

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Poster

The project poster has been designed as a visual aid and informative adornment for events such as conferences where CIRC-PACK has a booth/stand presence, as well as meetings which are of a more scientific nature. However, if requested by a project partner for another use, then ICLEI Europe will furnish that partner with the poster as needed.

The poster features the Circpack logo at the top, followed by the tagline "FROM WASTE TO RESOURCE". The main text describes the project's goal: "The CIRC-PACK project aims to develop a more sustainable plastic packaging value chain, producing breakthrough materials and innovative designs for the circular economy of the future." Below this, three integrated DEMO CASES are highlighted with images and labels: A (Plastics from Renewable Resources), B (Eco-friendly Packaging Designs), and C (Enhanced Sorting and Recycling). The bottom section includes contact information (info@circpack.eu, @circ_economy #circpack, linkedin.com/groups/12055948), a QR code, a disclaimer, and a list of project partners.

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Roll-up banner

The project disposes of two 'roll-ups'/ roll-up banners for use at various events: one for CIRCE in its capacity as project co-ordinator, and one for ICLEI Europe as work package lead for communications and dissemination activities.

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2.3 Communications: Templates for Word and PowerPoint

In the preparation of all manner of official CIRC-PACK documents (i.e. meeting minutes, reports, deliverables), a series of templates have been created and provided to partners – notably for Word documents (see below) and PowerPoint presentations (see 2.4.).

Agenda of the Meeting

SUBJECT		
N° MEETING		
DATE	DD/00/Month YYYY	
PLACE	Building Address - zip code City, Country	
STARTING TIME	Month DD/00 of TIME	
FINISHING TIME	Month DD/00 of TIME	
ATTENDANTS		
NAME	ENTITY	COUNTRY
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• CIRC'E	ES
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• AITIP	ES
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• NOVAMONT	IT
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• IASPER	IT
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• MBP	IT
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• BULMAGA	NE
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• TECHNO	ES
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• AIRPLAST	CR
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• SAGA	ES
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• SARONIA	CR
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• FATER	IT
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• FAVOR	ES
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• CRF	IT
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• DAPP	IT
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• BCO	ES
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• SCOBABEE	CR
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• SUEIA	CR
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• KARTAL	TR
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• CALAF	ES
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• OCU	ES
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• ICLEI	GE
• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	• PLASTIPOLIS	FR

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

AGENDA

DD/00/Month YYYY

Item	Time	Subject	Speaker
1	00:00 h	• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	NAME
2	00:00 h	• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet • Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	NAME
3	00:00 h	• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet • Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet • Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	NAME
4	00:00 h	• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	NAME
5	00:00 h	• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet • Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet • Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	NAME
6	00:00 h	• Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet	NAME

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CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

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MEETING MINUTES

Minutes of the Meeting

SUBJECT		
N° MEETING		
DATE	00/00/2017	
PLACE	Building Address - Zip code City, Country	
STARTING TIME	Month 00/01 of TIME	
FINISHING TIME	Month 00/01 of TIME	
ATTENDANTS		
NAME	ENTITY	COUNTRY
• 00000 00000 00000	• CIRC-CE	ES
• 00000 00000 00000	• AITIP	IT
• 00000 00000 00000	• NOVAMONT	IT
• 00000 00000 00000	• MIFP	ME
• 00000 00000 00000	• BIOMANCA	ES
• 00000 00000 00000	• TECNIO	CR
• 00000 00000 00000	• INFILAST	ES
• 00000 00000 00000	• SADA	CR
• 00000 00000 00000	• SARCHISA	IT
• 00000 00000 00000	• MATER	ES
• 00000 00000 00000	• MANDOR	IT
• 00000 00000 00000	• CIP	IT
• 00000 00000 00000	• EUPY	FR
• 00000 00000 00000	• SCORCHEES	ES
• 00000 00000 00000	• BUREAU	FR
• 00000 00000 00000	• LABRAL	FR
• 00000 00000 00000	• CALAF	ES
• 00000 00000 00000	• OCCU	ES
• 00000 00000 00000	• ICLEI	GB
• 00000 00000 00000	• PLASTIPOLIS	FR

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

MEETING MINUTES

AGENDA

Item	Title	Speaker
1	00000 00000 00000	00000
2	00000 00000 00000	00000
3	00000 00000 00000	00000
4	00000 00000 00000	00000
5	00000 00000 00000	00000
6	00000 00000 00000	00000

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

MEETING MINUTES

COMMENTS AND AGREEMENTS

Item	Topic	Action
1	00000 00000 00000	00000
2	00000 00000 00000	00000
3	00000 00000 00000	00000
4	00000 00000 00000	00000

ANNEX I: TITLE

00000 00000 00000

CIRC-PACK - Towards circular economy in the plastic packaging value chain

2.4 Generic project PowerPoint presentation

A crucial component of communicating on and disseminating information on the CIRC-PACK project, PowerPoint presentations at conferences and meetings must be both consistent in terms of visual identity and content to be professional and useful. Below are some exemplars of slides from the project's generic PowerPoint presentation. This gives an idea of both the visual identity of this project with the template being used, and also the importance of consistent messaging in terms of content.

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<p>CIRC-PACK A new circular economy for the plastic packaging sector</p> <p>Problems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited natural resources, increasing prices → efficient use needed Plastic produced remains on Earth ending up in landfill <p>Solution:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> From a make-take-dispose to a circular economy approach covering the whole product lifecycle Materials maintain their value for as long as possible and are recovered within the same value chain EU targets by 2030: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> recycle 75% packaging waste reduce landfill to 10% of municipal waste 					
<p>Demo case A: Bio-based, biodegradable, recyclable plastics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New materials: biopolymers + existing biopolyesters + bioadditives With enhanced functionalities: meeting product requirements <i>Mechanical / barrier properties, temperature variation resistance</i> Tested producing 5 packaging formats using different technologies THF separation and potential reuse Financial mechanisms, training, standardisation to overcome barriers Compostability, recyclability and material degradation assessment <p>↓</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greener and compostable packaging production 	<p>What are the benefits?</p> <table border="0"> <tr> <td> <p>TECHNOLOGICAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bridge research innovation gap: validating technologies for manufacture industry Better equipment and process performance Feasible customized solutions for different sectors / needs </td> <td> <p>ECONOMIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost reduction for materials + better performance = global competitiveness of EU plastics industry Savings from implementation of zero plastics to landfill by 2025 Reduction of dependence on fossil fuel variable cost </td> </tr> <tr> <td> <p>ENVIRONMENTAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreases in extraction / transport of raw materials Reduction of environmental impact of land filling Reduction of energy dependence on fossil fuel Resource efficiency and sustainability </td> <td> <p>SOCIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health, safety, well-being and quality of life Long-lasting innovative products for consumers Job creation Risk reduction in investment and decision making </td> </tr> </table>	<p>TECHNOLOGICAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bridge research innovation gap: validating technologies for manufacture industry Better equipment and process performance Feasible customized solutions for different sectors / needs 	<p>ECONOMIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost reduction for materials + better performance = global competitiveness of EU plastics industry Savings from implementation of zero plastics to landfill by 2025 Reduction of dependence on fossil fuel variable cost 	<p>ENVIRONMENTAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreases in extraction / transport of raw materials Reduction of environmental impact of land filling Reduction of energy dependence on fossil fuel Resource efficiency and sustainability 	<p>SOCIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health, safety, well-being and quality of life Long-lasting innovative products for consumers Job creation Risk reduction in investment and decision making
<p>TECHNOLOGICAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bridge research innovation gap: validating technologies for manufacture industry Better equipment and process performance Feasible customized solutions for different sectors / needs 	<p>ECONOMIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost reduction for materials + better performance = global competitiveness of EU plastics industry Savings from implementation of zero plastics to landfill by 2025 Reduction of dependence on fossil fuel variable cost 				
<p>ENVIRONMENTAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decreases in extraction / transport of raw materials Reduction of environmental impact of land filling Reduction of energy dependence on fossil fuel Resource efficiency and sustainability 	<p>SOCIAL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health, safety, well-being and quality of life Long-lasting innovative products for consumers Job creation Risk reduction in investment and decision making 				
<p>How does it work?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative work between partners along the value chain, from the public, private and non-profit sector, and research organisations 					

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 @circ_economy #circpack
[linkedin.com/groups/12055948](https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12055948)
 Contact: info@circpack.eu

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2.5 Videos

The CIRC-PACK project will produce to rounds of videos to aid and support the dissemination of the project. The first video, due for full completion towards the end of month 13 (May 2018), will constitute an animated video of approximately two minutes in length to introduce and promote the project, describe the project objectives and introduce the CIRC-PACK consortium.

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The second round of videos will constitute a set of short videos with real life video footage and animated features to outline the results of the project in more detail and in a more attractive manner than could be achieved with solely reports or written content. These videos will also be widely disseminated by ICLEI Europe and of course the other project partners.

2.6 Twitter Account

The CIRC-PACK project disposes of a shared Twitter account with the PlastiCircle Horizon 2020 project, since both are focused on plastics within the circular economy and the need to avoid splitting an audience which has the potential to be far larger with one consolidated Twitter platform. In this respect, even during the early stages of the project, the number of followers is increasing steadily and in an encouraging manner. ICLEI Europe manages this account (see below).

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Home Notifications Messages
Search Twitter
Go-funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework

Plastic Circular Economy
@circ_economy

Tweets **74**

Following **269**

Followers **175**

Likes **66**

Lists **0**

Moments **0**

Edit profile

Show this thread

Plastic Circular Economy @circ_economy · Apr 11

▼

In-depth discussions at #CIRCPACK's 'Waste to resource' focus groups in Brussels. For #plastics projects to be successful - whether on production, #sorting or #recycling - yes, we need infrastructure and technology, but public #information and awareness is key.

ICLEI Europe, Novamont, Fundación CIRCE and 6 others

1
7
10

Show this thread

Plastic Circular Economy @circ_economy · Apr 11

▼

Carlo Strazza of #CIRCPACK partner @RINA1861 is providing the Brussels audience with some key insights into the legislative barriers for the #recycling of #fossil based and biobased #plastics.

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3 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable 8.2 is intended to provide an accessible overview of the dissemination and communications materials that have been prepared in the first 12 months of the project. However, more detailed information or product .pdf files is available upon request from the appropriate desk officer(s) at the European Commission.

The products and materials outlined in this document constitute an important part of delivering a professional, credible and effective Horizon 2020 project by virtue of their importance to the project brand and of course the extent to which awareness is raised of the CIRC-PACK projects. In this regard, the second round of videos (M30) and leaflets and posters (M30) will provide valuable updates and project results at the appropriate time, thus allowing for even more extensive reporting and dissemination of information regarding the CIRC-PACK project.

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4 ANNEXES

ANNEX A: Press Pack – FAQs:

What is CIRC-PACK and why is it important?

CIRC-PACK is a project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 programme, which aims to improve the entire plastic packaging value chain from polymer production to end-of-life disposal, through the development of bio-based and recyclable plastics, and the improvement of recycling processes. By developing new bio-based and/or biodegradable plastics for the manufacture of a wide range of products, this project aims to reduce the environmental footprint of packaging. It will also improve the design of products to make sorting easier, and promote reuse and recycling; this way the recovery rates of plastic waste can increase and the quality of recycled plastics can improve – ultimately contributing to a more circular economy in the packaging sector.

What is different about this project? What are the innovations?

CIRC-PACK will address not only the improvement of plastic recycling, but the replacement of fossil-based polymers with bio-based and/or biodegradable plastics for certain applications. Essentially, it will introduce new innovative packing designs produced from biodegradable raw materials, so that multi-layer and multi-component packaging can be substituted by eco-packaging that is both more biodegradable and recyclable.

Crucially, the innovations proposed by CIRC-PACK will foster the development of market niches related to new plastic waste recycling opportunities and enable interlinkages between different value chains. In the future, this will lead to higher volumes of waste being diverted from landfill.

Furthermore, consumers from different countries will be involved throughout the project to ensure the social acceptance of the innovative solutions proposed by the project.

Who’s who in the plastic packaging value chain?

CIRC-PACK brings in stakeholders from the whole value chain of the plastic packaging sector and from different regions across Europe. The project consortium is composed of the following profiles:

- 1) **Plastic producers** – producers combine a large number of monomers to form polymer chains in a chemical process called ‘polymerisation’. The type of monomers and the structure of the resulting polymer define the polymer’s characteristics.
- 2) **Compounders** – compounders prepare plastic formulations by mixing and/or blending polymers and additives into process-ready pellets.
- 3) **Packaging manufacturers** – these companies design and manufacture packaging items.
- 4) **Brand owners** – the owners of brands (and consumer goods companies) package their products or goods. Then retailers put these packaged goods onto the market.
- 5) **Users** – the end user not only unpacks the product and (mostly) discards the packaging, but also makes purchasing decisions and decides whether innovate products stay on the market

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or fail. End users can also include public sector bodies, who can be a powerful force in stimulating demand for new products through their procurement activities.

- 6) **Resource management companies** – these companies collect consumer as well as commercial after-use materials (often mixed). This is done through: curb-side collection, bring systems, deposit systems, etc. After-use materials collected for recycling go to materials recovery facilities or sorting facilities where they are sorted into various ‘fractions’ (i.e. plastics by type, paper, glass, ferrous metals, non-ferrous metals, organics, etc.). The after-use plastic types that have been separated out are ‘baled’ for recycling.
- 7) **Reprocessors/ recyclers** – reprocessing and recycling specialists conduct additional sorting steps. In the case of mechanical recycling, the plastic material is shredded, cleaned, dried, sometimes sorted by colour, and compounded to be eventually re-granulated into process-ready pellets.

What is the difference between a bio-based and a biodegradable plastic?

It is important to remember that bio-based plastics are not biodegradable *per se* (i.e. bio-PET, bio-PVC), because the biodegradability property depends on the chemical structure and not on the raw material used (so biodegradable plastics are not necessarily bio-based, and can also be fossil-based).

- A **bio-based plastic** means that the plastic is partially made from a renewable raw material source (biomass). Since they are chemically identical to their conventional plastic counterparts – where there is a specific recycling stream for a specific plastic type (i.e. PE or PET) – the bio-based alternatives (bio-PE, bio-PET) can be recycled together with the conventional plastic.
- A **biodegradable plastic** refers to the behaviour of the plastic at its end of life. Biodegradation is the chemical process in which microorganisms available in the environment convert the plastic into water, CO₂ and compost. The speed of the process depends on the conditions (temperature, humidity and so on).

What are multilayer and multi-material packaging and what are their drawbacks? How will the CIRC-PACK project deal with them?

Multilayer packaging is packaging made of several, indistinguishable plastic layers (PET, EVO, PP), i.e. some plastic trays containing fresh food. Because of its complexity, this mix of different polymers is currently not easily and/or commercially recyclable. Within the CIRC-PACK project, some widely used multilayer food packaging formats, such as films, will be replaced by bio-plastic. But while providing the same functionalities and properties as conventional multilayer packaging, these bio-plastics would be compostable.

Multi-material packaging, on the other hand, makes use of different materials within the same packaging format, i.e. laminated cardboard with plastic film (which provides barrier properties to the cardboard). This combination of materials, hardly separable, hampers recycling. The solution developed to overcome this problem in the CIRC-PACK project is the use of a new biopolymer which can be recovered from the conventional cardboard recycling process, without hampering this recycling.

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How is CIRC-PACK relevant for sectors other than packaging?

The project will aim to increase the amount of recycled materials from the plastic packaging value chain. Moreover, the improved sorting and processing protocols developed in CIRC-PACK to increase recyclability and quality of recycled plastic materials, may 'spill over' and be used in other sectors. A market for secondary materials will be developed and business models and regulatory best practices will be identified, which may impact other sectors. CIRC-PACK results could also be directly applied to other value chains using materials similar to those in the plastic packaging value chain.

In addition, the CIRC-PACK evaluation methodology (for the evaluation of different innovations in the project) will allow experts to assess the impacts of changes to the main influencing parameters along the value chain. This evaluation methodology can be applied to various different value chains.

How can packaged product customers contribute to a circular economy where the plastic packaging sector is concerned?

In environmental terms, the use of bio-based products helps reduce dependency on fossil fuels and decreases emissions stemming from combustion of conventional plastic waste. Furthermore, bio-based products have other benefits such as boosting rural economies and contributing to a greener economy.

Moreover, increased recycling of plastics (whether bio-based or conventional), reduces the volume of wastes found in landfills, reduces the consumption of valuable virgin materials and promotes the generation of eco-friendly job opportunities.

As a consumer or stakeholder, the use of bio-based packaging materials will promote the growth of the bio-plastic sector (which also produces materials for other applications) – with the aforementioned environmental benefits. Moreover, if consumers can avoid the use of non-recyclable materials, this will help promote efficiencies in sorting and recycling plastic wastes. In turn, this can reduce landfill waste volumes and also raw material consumption in the plastics sector.

So how do I identify bio-based products or even non-recyclable materials?

Bio-based products can be identified by several standards and eco-labels (which are different in each country). Some of these standards are focused on the origin of the material (i.e. they are obtained from sustainable or bio-based raw materials) while others are focused on the biodegradability (i.e. they are biodegradable or compostable either at home or in industrial plants).

As for recycling, 'multi-materials' such as laminated board or other multilayer materials are more difficult to recycle than 'monomaterials'. Concerning plastics, materials used in packaging can be identified by triangle-shaped recycling icons, which specify a category number depending on the composition of that plastic. Materials in categories 1 (PETE), 2 (HDPE), 4 (LDPE) and 5 (PP) are easier to recycle than those in categories 3 (PVC), 6 (PS) and 7 ('Other', including multilayer plastics and plastics with hazardous additives).